

Individualisation, A Medico-Social and Psychological Approach

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INTRODUCTION

Individualisation is a condition where society as a whole increasingly adapts to the circumstances, preferences, and needs of each individual while acknowledging the individuals rights to this and encourages individuals to use it. The aim of my findings is not here to disrespect any professions or hurt anyone's believe nor question on any life saving works of doctors but what I strongly want to convey is the need of changes in the approaches of treatment so that we are able to reach every person with the need of health care, where treatments are accessible to every group and class of people and more importantly a disease free environment. Not only in the field of healthcare but also a change in the society which will help in breaking many age old stereotypes.

➤ Individualisation in Medicine-Genetic approach:- A. Personalized medicine,

also termed individualised medicine, is a medical procedure that separates patients into different groups—with medical decisions, practices, interventions and/or products being tailored to the individual patient based on their predicted response or risk of disease. The process might take a longer period and might take hours and maybe a day, and in that same period of time a doctor might be able check 9-10 patient but the question arises here; what kind of healthcare facility are we providing to a person who completely and blindly relies on us for cure, quantity or quality? Although most of the variation between individuals has no effect on health, an individual's health stems from genetic variation

ABSTRACT

The Earth! 4th planet of the solar system and suppose to be only planet that supports lives which makes it the most unique and separate from rest of the planet but that doesn't mean other planet are less. Every planet has its own unique character that makes it different. Exactly in a same way we are 7.6 billion (i.e 7,600,000,000 people) heads; breathing, walking, talking, working in the Earth, just like those nine planets with there on uniqueness; we are humans with our own complex body mechanism and functions. No doubt we all belong to same species but we too differ in our genetic makeup, response, appearance, emotion, expressions, voice, culture, traditions, response to diseases, fingerprints, our cuisine, personality trait, rituals, dressing, habits, hobbies, mental ability etcetera. So the question here is why there is same medical technology, medical approach, and same medical protocol for every human being? We will totally agree with the fact that we all are different in one way or the other and our body needs and demands vary from person to person still there no change in the treatment procedures. As we are advancing with our lifestyle so as the diseases, and our approaches are making those causative agents more and more resistance which is helping to adapt with the new environment.

This brings the need of individualising the technology to every extent possible using the medico social and psychological approach. So that we'll be able eradicate not just the symptoms but the disease in whole.

KEYWORDS: Individualization, Psychosocial approach of individualization

with behaviours and influences from the environment. Modern advances in personalized medicine rely on technology that confirms a patient's fundamental biology, DNA, RNA, or protein, which ultimately leads to confirming disease. For example, personalised techniques such as genome sequencing can reveal mutations in DNA that influence diseases ranging from cystic fibrosis to cancer. Another method, called RNA sequencing, can show which RNA molecules are involved with specific diseases. Unlike DNA, levels of **RNA can change in response to the environment**. Therefore, sequencing RNA can provide a broader understanding of a person's state of health. Recent studies have linked genetic differences between individuals to RNA expression, translation, and protein levels.

In order for physicians to know if a mutation is connected to a certain disease, researchers often do a study called a "genome-wide association study" (GWAS). A GWAS study will look at one disease, and then sequence the genome of many patients with that particular disease to look for shared mutations in the genome. Mutations that are determined to be related to a disease by a GWAS study can then be used to diagnose that disease in future patients, by looking at their genome sequence to find that same mutation.

Having the genetic content of an individual will allow better guided decisions in determining the source of the disease and thus treating it or preventing its progression. This will be extremely useful for diseases like Alzheimer's or cancers

that are thought to be linked to certain mutations in our DNA.

➤ **Individualisation: Medical Approach (Homeopathy):-**
The concept of disease in homeopathy is disease due to total affection of mind and body. Mind and body are dynamic and complexly interlinked; each one influencing the other and acting together. Neither mind nor body falls ill individually. Now we are start learning that prolong emotional stress (too much desire, anger, greed, pride, jealousy, suspicion, etc.) can lead to upset stomach, difficulty digesting food, poor nutrient absorption, sleeplessness, weaken immune system, etc.

The emotional state closely relates to endocrine glands and nerves, which influence over the working of the physical body.

Thus, homeopathy medicine is as psycho-somatic medicine and is excellent for psycho-somatic diseases such as Migraine, Asthma, Peptic ulcer, Allergy, Ulcerative colitis, etc.

➤ **Individualisation: Medical Approach (Ayurveda):-**
Ayurveda, the traditional Indian medicinal system remains the most ancient yet living traditions with sound philosophical and experimental basis. It is a science of life with a holistic approach to health and personalized medicine. It is known to be a complete medical system that comprised physical, psychological, philosophical, ethical, and spiritual health. In Ayurveda, each cell is considered to be inherently an essential expression of pure intelligence hence called self-healing science.

In addition, to the self-healing concept, the use of herbal treatment is equally important in this Indian traditional system of medicine.

➤ **Individualisation: Social approach:-**
Although physicians are just beginning to see the promise of genetic medicine coming to fruition and can't hide their excitement for the technology, the patients are asking for personalized care: a holistic approach that considers an individual's physical, mental, and spiritual well-being. This perspective considers psychological, religious, and ethical challenges that may arise as the precision of preventive medicine improves.

Understanding current areas of potential conflict between religion and medicine can be informative when anticipating the public's concerns regarding personalized medicine. The most extreme conflict currently is between the medical community and churches that reject modern medicine, such as the Indiana-based Faith Assembly and the Christian Science Church. Personalized medicine will not be relevant to these individuals as they reject most medical assistance. The majority of the estimated 172 children who died between 1975 and 1995 because prayer was used in lieu of medical care were from such churches. Another group of people who may challenge personalized medicine are those who question evolution and, by association, genetics.

In a June 2008 Pew Forum poll, 45% of Americans rejected evolution as the best explanation of the origins of human life. Population genetics, which will form the basis for much of the scientific advances in personalized medicine, relies on certain tenets of heredity that stem from evolutionary

biology. As such, certain religious groups may reject personalized medicine, while the majority of patients and physicians are likely to continue to accept the technologies while distancing themselves from the theoretical foundations. Atheists may view illness as a statistically based combination of genetic and environmental factors, while believers of certain religions may view illness as punishment or a test of faith by a higher power, as illustrated in the story of Job. Many Pentecostal and Charismatic Christians envision Satan as the author of sickness and Christ as their healer; in this framework, they view spiritual and physical healing as complementary rather than conflicting. Although the majority of religious institutions, including Roman Catholic and conservative Protestant churches, have been supportive of DNA-based research and diagnostics, this view could change if personalized medicine appears to conflict with the sanctity of human life.

➤ **Individualisation: Medico-Social Approach:**
Indians have been keeping track of their DNA line, knowingly or unknowingly, through the GOTRA tracking system. In most of tribes and religions two people from same kula or gotra are not allowed to marry as they are considered to be sharing same ancestors and some similarities in the genetic sequences, in a way if we see the reason is very scientific that's because according to genetic science the parents who are close relatives and siblings are like to be give birth to a child who are mentally retarded, suffer from various genetic conditions, and like to show grater mutation in the genetic makeup which leads to various deformities. So as to avoid all this; from very ancient time Rajgurus have kept the track of gotra.

This tracking of DNA line can significantly help in individualising medicines based on the GOTRA of an individual.

➤ **Individualisation: Psychological approach:-**
The biggest challenges in implementing these concepts would be the most difficult task as there are many ruler areas where the basic accesses to healthcare facility is stilled believed to be taboo, people believe more on tantras, black magic, shamans for thir cure. These is due to lack of awareness, and also the mentality of people under the pressure of there elders or in the name shake of age old practices.

Implementing personalized medicine will require attention to psychological issues already encountered by genetic counsellors and physicians. Before genetic testing was possible, 60%–75% of individuals at risk for Huntington disease indicated that they would undergo testing, but when a test became available only 3%–21% opted to be tested. In cancer where positive genetic testing could encourage women or their daughters to participate in vigorous screening or pre-emptive surgery (such as mastectomy), testing is not universally accepted. Even among insured women with recently diagnosed breast cancer, a significant number (approximately 20%–30%) refuse genetic testing proper psychological counselling is very important for individualisation. Understanding the patient will make the medicines holistic, personalised and effective. Also, making the patients connect to themselves will make the medicine much more effective as a person in peace produces minimal level of stress hormone and make the medicine work with least hindrance.

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